

VHDL Reference

An extensive reference guide for VHDL basics that includes essential language framework, data types, operators, and primary programming constructs, including code examples.

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VHDL is a case insensitive **and** strongly typed language

1. Compilation Units

Every VHDL design file consists of three primary parts: Library, Entity, and Architecture.

- Library Usage Declarations
- Entity Declarations
- Architecture Declarations
- Package Declarations
- Configuration Declarations

2. Entity Declaration = IO of a design

The entity defines the public interface of your circuit - its input and output ports. It's where you declare all your design's external variables. The semicolon acts as a separator, with no semicolon on the last port.

```
entity n_input_nand is generic (n : integer := 2);
port (data : in bit_vector(1 to n);
      result : out bit);
end n_input_nand
-- port directions: in | out | inout | buffer | linkage
```

3. RTL Architecture = Implementation

Describes the internal behavior and logic of an entity. This is where you define how the outputs are derived from the inputs. RTL code creates hardware and/or logic. RTL code contains assignments and process statements

```
architecture behave of n_input_nand is
-- declarations
begin
-- concurrent statements
end behave;
```

4. VHDL Operators

logical operators : **and, or, xor, nand, nor, xnor, not**
relational operators : **=, /=, <, <=, >, >=**
shift left/right logical operators: **sl, srl**
shift left/right arithmetic operators: **sla, sra**
rotate left/right logical operators: **rol, ror**
other operators: **+, -, &, *, **, /, mod, abs, rem**
eg. &: concatenation, **'1' & "10"** = "110"
******: exponentiation, **2 ** 3** = 8
rem: remainder, **7 rem 2** = 1
mod: division modulo, **5 mod 3** = 2

5. Data Types

VHDL strongly typed. **STD_LOGIC** the flexible type for digital design

Type	Description	Values	Library Required
BIT	Simple binary value '0' and '1' only		std.standard
STD_LOGIC	Enhanced logic '0', '1', 'Z', 'X', 'U' IEEE.STD_LOGIC_1164		
STD_LOGIC_VECTOR	Array of STD_LOGIC "110" STD_LOGIC_1164		

Vectors: Arrays of a base type. Range can be DOWNTO (descending) or TO (ascending).

```
SIGNAL my_bus: STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(7 DOWNTO 0);
SIGNAL data: STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(0 TO 7);
my_bus <= "10101100";
my_bus <= x"AC";
my_bus <= (7=>'1', 3=>'1', OTHERS=>'0');
```

A) Predefined Data Types bit
'0' and '1' bit_vector
Array of "bit" **boolean**
true and false

Character	7-bit ASCII
integer	signed 32 bit at least
natural	integer >= 0
positive	integer > 0
real	Floating point, min : +1e38 to -1e38
string	Array of characters
time	hr, min, sec, ms, us, ns, ps, fs

B) User Defined Data Types

type range is range 0 to 100000

units

```
meter; -- base unit
kilometer = 1000 meter;
end units distance;
type number is integer;
type voltage is range 0 to 5;
type current is range 1000 downto 0;
type d_bus is array (range <>) of bit;
type instruction is record
opcode: bit; operand: bit;
end record;
type int_file is file of integer;
type pointer_to_integer is access integer;
subtype positive_number is integer range 0 to 100000
type fourval is (X, L, H, Z);
subtype resolve_n is resolve twoval;
```

C) Working with Numbers

Arithmetic operations like addition and subtraction can only be performed on data of the same type. A **STD_LOGIC_VECTOR** must be type-cast to a numeric type like signed or unsigned before you can perform math on it. For this, you must use the **IEEE.NUMERIC_STD.ALL** library.

```
SIGNAL a, b, sum : STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(7 DOWNTO 0);
sum <= STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(UNSIGNED(a) + UNSIGNED(b));
sum <= STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(SIGNED(a) + SIGNED(b));
result <= STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(UNSIGNED(data) + 1);
result <= STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(UNSIGNED(data) - 1);
result <= STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(UNSIGNED(data) SLL 1);
```

D) Custom Data Types

VHDL allows to define your own data types for better clarity and modeling. Useful for modeling memories. A custom type to model a small memory with 256 entries. Each entry is an integer from 0 to 255.

```
TYPE memory_array IS ARRAY(0 TO 255) OF INTEGER RANGE 0 TO 255;
TYPE state_type IS (IDLE, ACTIVE, ERROR, RESET);
SIGNAL my_memory : memory_array;
SIGNAL current_state : state_type := IDLE;
my_memory(10) <= 255;
data_out <= my_memory(addr);
```

6. Declarations

```
constant bus_width : integer := 32
variable read_flag : bit := 0;
-- only in processes
-- and subprograms
signal clock " bit;
file f3: int_file open write_mode is "test.out";
alias enable: bit is addr(31);
attribute delay : time;
component n_input_nand
generic (n : integer := 2);
port (data : in bit_vector(1 to n); result : out bit);
end component n_input_nand;
function square (i : integer) return integer;
for store : use configuration latch;
```

7. Attributes

```
-- type my_array is array (9 downto 0) of any_type;
-- variable an_array: my_array;
-- type fourval is ('0', '1', 'Z', 'X');
-- signal sig : sigtype;
-- constant T : time := 10 ns;
```

Attribute	Result type	Result
my_array'high	any_type	9
my_array'left	any_type	9
my_array'low	any_type	0
my_array'right	any_type	0
my_array'ascending	boolean	false
my_array'length	integer	10
my_array'range	integer	9 downto 0
my_array'reverse_range		
integer		0 to 9
fourval'leftof('0')	fourval	error
fourval'leftof('1')	fourval	'0'
fourval'pos('Z')	integer	2
fourval'pred('1')	fourval	'0'
fourval'rightof('1')	fourval	'Z'
fourval'succ('Z')	fourval	'X'
fourval'val(3)	fourval	'X'
sig'active	boolean	

```
True if activity on sig
sig'delayed(T) sigtype
Copy of sig delayed by T
sig'driving_value sigtype
Value of driver on sig
sig'event boolean
True if event on sig
sig'last_active time
Time since last activity
sig'last_event time
```

Time since last event	
sig*last_value	sigtype
Value before last event	
sig*quiet(T)	boolean
Activity (now – T) to now	
sig*stable(T)	boolean
Event (now – T) to now	
sig*transactio	bit
Toggles on activity on sig	

8. Assigning Values

```
A_sl <= '1'; -- Character literal
B_slv <= "1111"; -- string literal
C_slv <= X"FF"; -- hex. 4 bits per character
E_slv <= (others => '1'); -- aggregate
L_int <= 15; -- universal integer
M_int <= 16#F#; -- base literal (16 = base)
N_bool <= TRUE; -- boolean only true or false
```

9. Modeling Styles: Structural vs Behavioral

You can implement logic in two main ways: **Structural Modeling**, which describes a circuit by connecting instances of pre-existing components. It focuses on the netlist or schematic view of the hardware. Structural code connects lower levels of a design. Structural code has three pieces: component declarations, signal declarations, and component instances (creates the connectivity).

architecture Structural of MuxReg is -- Component Declarations

component Mux8x2

```
port (
    Sel : In std_logic ;
    I0, I1 : In unsigned(7 downto 0);
    Y : Out unsigned(7 downto 0)
```

```
);
end component ;
component Reg8
```

```
port (
    Clk : In std_logic ;
    D : In unsigned(7 downto 0);
    Q : Out unsigned(7 downto 0)
);
```

```
end component ;
-- Signal Declarations
signal Mux : unsigned(7 downto 0);
begin
```

-- Component Instantiations

-- Named Association

Mux8x2_1: Mux8x2

```
port map (
    Sel => Sel,
    I0 => A,
    I1 => B,
    Y => Mux
```

```
);
-- Positional Association
```

```
Reg8_1: Reg8
    port map (Clk, Mux, Y);
end Structural;
```

Behavioral Modeling: Describes the circuit's behavior directly using logic equations and processes. It focuses on the flow of

data and the algorithm.

ARCHITECTURE behavioral OF multiplexer IS

BEGIN

output <= a WHEN sel = '0' ELSE b;

END ARCHITECTURE;

ARCHITECTURE structural OF multiplexer IS

COMPONENT and_gate PORT (x, y : IN STD_LOGIC; z : OUT STD_LOGIC);

COMPONENT or_gate PORT (x, y : IN STD_LOGIC; z : OUT STD_LOGIC);

SIGNAL not_sel, and1_out, and2_out : STD_LOGIC;

BEGIN

U1: and_gate PORT MAP (a, not_sel, and1_out);

U2: and_gate PORT MAP (b, sel, and2_out);

U3: or_gate PORT MAP (and1_out, and2_out, output);

not_sel <= NOT sel;

END ARCHITECTURE;

Generics: Creating Reusable Components

A **generic** is a parameter you can pass to an entity to make it more flexible, like a global constant for that instance. This allows you to create configurable components.

ENTITY n_bit_register IS

GENERIC (N : INTEGER := 8);

PORT (

d : IN STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(N-1 DOWNTO 0);

q : OUT STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(N-1 DOWNTO 0)

);

END ENTITY n_bit_register;

10. Concurrent Statements: coded in the architecture.

A) Signal Assignments: Expression is evaluated immediately. Value is assigned one delta cycle later.

B) Simple Assignment =logic and/or wires

```
Z <= AddReg ;
Sel <= SelA and SelB ;
YL <= A(6 downto 0) & '0'; --Shift Lt
YR <= '0' & A(7 downto 1); --Shift Rt
SR <= SI_sl & A(7 downto 1); --Shift In
```

C) Conditional Assignment

```
Mux2 <=
    A when (Sel1 = '1' and Sel2 = '1')
  else B or C ;
ZeroDet <= '1' when Cnt = 0 else '0';
```

D) Selected Assignment

```
with MuxSel select
Mux41 <= A when "00", B when "01", C when "10",
D when "11", 'X' when others;
```

E) Process = Container of Sequential Code

Must have either a sensitivity list or wait statement. Combinational logic requires all inputs (signals read in the process) to be on the sensitivity list. The "is" following the sensitivity list is optional.

Mux : process (MuxSel, A, B, C, D) is

```
begin
    case MuxSel is
        when "00" => Y <= A ;
        when "01" => Y <= B ;
        when "10" => Y <= C ;
        when "11" => Y <= D ;
```

when others => Y <= 'X';

end case;

end process;

state_mach: process (state) -- label is optional

-- variable declarations

begin

-- sequential statements

end process;

U1_n_input_nand : n_input_nand

generic map (n => 2)

port map (data => my_data;

result => my_res);

top_block : block

-- declaration

begin

-- concurrent statements

end block;

label1: for i in 1 to 3 generate

label2: nand2(a(i), b(i), c(i));

end generate

label3: if (i < 4) generate

label4: nor2(a(i), b(i), c(i));

end generate;

11. Sequential Statements: Contained in processes and subprograms

A) Signal Assignment

Z <= AddReg;

Sel <= Sel1 and Sel2;

VHDL-2008 allows conditional and selected assignments in sequential statements

B) Variable Assignment

Expression is evaluated and assigned immediately.

MuxSel := S1 & S0;

C) IF Statement

if (in1 = '1') then

NextState <= S1 ; Out1 <= '1' ;

elsif (in2 = '1' and in3 = '1') then

NextState <= S2 ;

elsif (in4 and in5) = '1' then

NextState <= S3 ;

else

NextState <= S4 ;

end if ;

An IF statement can have one or more signal assignments per branch.

Prior to VHDL-2008, the conditional expression must be boolean. With

VHDL- 2008 it may also be bit or std_ulogic (std_logic).

D) Case Statement

Mux : process (S1, S0, A, B, C, D)

variable MuxSel :

std_logic_vector(1 downto 0) ;

begin

MuxSel := S1 & S0 ;

case MuxSel is

when "00" => Y <= A;

```

when "01" => Y <= B;
when "10" => Y <= C;
when "11" => Y <= D;
when others => Y <= 'X';

end case ;
end process ;

```

- E) Asynchronous Reset Flip-Flop.** Asynchronous reset is specified before the clock. Clock and reset must be on the sensitivity list.

```

RegProc : process ( Clk, nReset)
begin
if (nReset = '0') then
    AReg <= '0';
    BReg <= '0';
elsif rising_edge(Clk) then
    if LoadEn = '1' then
        AReg <= A;
        BReg <= B;
    end if;
end if;
end process;

```

- F) Synchronous Reset Flip-Flop.** Synchronous reset is specified after the clock. Only clock must be on the sensitivity list.

```

RegProc: process (Clk)
begin
    if rising_edge(Clk) then
        if (nReset = '0') then
            AReg <= '0';
        elsif LoadEn = '1' then
            AReg <= A;
        end if;
    end if;
end process;

```

- G) For Loop:** Loop index does not need to be declared. For synthesis, loop index must be integer.

```

RevAProc : process(A)
begin
    for i in 0 to 7 loop
        RevA(7 - i) <= A(i);
    end loop;
end process;

```

- H) Creating Clock**

```

Clk1 <= not Clk1 after 10 ns;
ClkProc : process
begin
    Clk2 <= '0'
    wait for 10 ns;
Clk2 <= '1';
    wait for 10 ns;
end process;

```

- D) Wait Until and after:** Wait stops a process for at least a delta cycle. Wait until Clk = '1' finds the next rising edge of clock and is used extensively in testbenches. Signal assignments using "after" always project a value on a signal. "After" never causes a process to stop.

```

TestProc : process begin

```

```

wait until Clk = '1';
Addr <= "000" after tpd_Clk_Addr;
wait until Clk = '1';
Addr <= "001" after tpd_Clk_Addr;
-- and so on ...
wait for tperiod_clk * 5;
report "Test Done" severity failure;
end process;

```

12. Generate Statement

The GENERATE statement acts like a for loop for creating multiple instances of concurrent hardware statements, perfect for repetitive structures.

```

ARCHITECTURE structural OF parallel_adder IS
BEGIN
    gen_label: FOR i IN 0 TO 7 GENERATE
        and_instance: ENTITY work.and_gate PORT MAP (a(i), b(i), c(i));
    END GENERATE gen_label;
END ARCHITECTURE;

```

13. Component Instantiation

This is the process of using a pre-defined entity as a component in another design. Each instance is a unique copy and must be given a unique label to differentiate it.

```

COMPONENT counter IS
    PORT (
        clk : IN STD_LOGIC;
        reset : IN STD_LOGIC;
        count : OUT STD_LOGIC_VECTOR(3 DOWNTO 0)
    );
END COMPONENT;
U_Counter: counter PORT MAP (
    clk => system_clock,
    reset => system_reset,
    count => counter_output );

```

14. Concurrent and Sequential Statements

```

enable <= select after 1 ns;
assert ( a = b )
report "a is not equal to b"
severity note;
-- severity levels : note | warning | error | failure

```

15. Package Declarations

```

package two_level is
-- type, signal, functions declarations
end two_level;
package body two_level is
-- subprogram definitions
end two_level;

```

16. Library Usage Declarations

```

-- using the two_level package.
library work;
use work.two_level.all; -- all objects used
use work.two_level.vcc; -- only the "vcc" object used

```

```

Subprograms
function bool_2_2level ( boolean : in_bool )
return two_level is
variable return_val : two_level;

```

begin

```

if ( in_bool = true ) then
    return_val := high;
else
    return_val := low;
end if;
return return_val;
end bool_2_2level;

```

procedure clock_buffer

```

( signal local_clk: inout bit;
signal clk_pin: in bit;
constant clock_skew: in time ) is
begin -- example of side effects in a procedure
global_clk <= local_clk
after clk_skew; local_clk <= clk_pin;
end clock_buffer;

```

17. Predefined Subprograms

```

enable <= '1' when ( now < 2 ns ) else '0';
variable ptoi : pointer_to_integer;
ptoi := new integer; -- usage of new deallocate (ptoi);
variable status : file_open_status; file my_file : int_file;
file_open( status, my_file, "in.dat", read_mode );
end_file ( my_file ); -- returns true/false
variable int_var : integer;
read ( my_file, int_var );
file_close ( my_file );

```

18. Configuration Declarations

```

configuration input_8 of n_nand is for customizable
for a1 : nand_2
use entity work.nand_2 ( n_nand_arch );
end for; end for;
end input_8;

```

11.

19. Non-synthesizable Constructs

Most tools will not synthesize : access, after, alias, assert, bus, disconnect, file, guarded, inertial, impure, label, linkage, new, on, open, postponed, pure, reject, report, severity, shared, transport, units, with.

20. Standard Packages

A) Common Packages

```

Usage Abbr. Source
use std.standard.all ; -- * std IEEE
ieee.std_logic_1164.all ; 1164 IEEE
use ieee.numeric_std.all ; ns IEEE
use ieee.numeric_std_unsigned.all ; nsu IEEE
use ieee.std_logic_arith.all ; sla Shareware
use ieee.std_logic_unsigned.all ; sls Shareware
use std.textio.all ; textio IEEE
use ieee.std_logic_textio.all ; - Shareware
VHDL-2008 adds packages for fixed and floating point.

```

B) Common Synthesizable Types

```

Type / Abbreviation Value Package
std_logic / sl U X 0 1 Z W L H - 1164
std_logic_vector / slv array of std_logic 1164

```

signed / sv array of std_logic ns, sla
 unsigned / uv array of std_logic ns, sla
 boolean / bool (False, True) std
 integer / int -(2³¹ - 1) to 2³¹ - 1 std
 natural / int0+ 0 to 2³¹ - 1 std
 line access string textio
 Enumerated type StateType is (S0, S1, S2, S3) ;

C) IEEE.STD_LOGIC_1164 Package

type **std_ulogic** is ('U', 'X', '0', '1', 'W', 'L', 'H') ;
 type **std_ulogic_vector** is array
 (natural range <>) of std_ulogic ;
 function **resolved** (s : std_ulogic_vector) return std_ulogic ; subtype
std_logic is resolved std_ulogic ;
 type **std_logic_vector** is array
 (natural range <>) of std_logic ;
 function **to_bit** (s : std_ulogic ; xmap : bit := '0') return bit ;
 function **to_bitvector** : std_logic_vector ; xmap : bit := '0')
 return bitvector ;
 function **to_stdlogicvector** (b : bit_vector) return std_logic_vector ;
 function **rising_edge** (signal s : std_ulogic) return boolean ;
 function **falling_edge** (signal s : std_ulogic) return boolean ;
 function **is_x** (s : std_logic_vector) return boolean ;

D) STD.TEXTIO Package

type **line** access string ;
 type **text** is file of string ;
 type **side** is (right, left) ;
 subtype **width** is natural ;
 file **input** : text open read_mode is "std_input" ;
 file **output** : text open write_mode is "std_output" ;
 procedure **readline** (file f : text ; I : out line) ;
 procedure **writeline** (file f : text ; I : in line) ;
 procedure **read** (I : in out line ;
 value : out bit ;
 good : out boolean) ;
 procedure **write** (I : in out line ; value : in bit ;
 justified : in side := right ;
 field : in width := 0) ;

-- The type of "value" can be bit_vector | boolean | character | integer |
 real | string | time. There is no standard package for textio operations on
 std_logic. Tools vendors may provide their own.

E) IEEE.NUMERIC_STD Package

type **unsigned** is array (natural range <>) of std_logic ;
 type **signed** is array (natural range <>) of std_logic ;
 function **shift_left** (arg : unsigned ; count : natural)
 return unsigned ;
 -- Other functions: **shift_right()**, **rotate_left()**, **rotate_right()**
 function **rsize** (arg : signed ; new_size : natural) return signed ;

21. TESTBENCH

library ieee ;
 use ieee.std_logic_1164.all ;
 use ieee.numeric_std.all ;
 entity **tb_counter** is
 end **tb_counter** ;
 architecture behavioral of **tb_counter** is

```

-- Component declaration
component counter is
  port (
    clk      : in std_logic;
    reset    : in std_logic;
    enable   : in std_logic;
    count    : out std_logic_vector(7 downto 0) );
end component;
-- Testbench signals
signal clk      : std_logic := '0';
signal reset   : std_logic := '1';
signal enable  : std_logic := '0';
signal count   : std_logic_vector(7 downto 0);
-- Clock period
constant clk_period : time := 10 ns;
begin
-- Unit Under Test instantiation
uut: counter
  port map (
    clk      => clk,
    reset    => reset,
    enable   => enable,
    count    => count
  );
-- Clock generation
clk_proc: process
begin
  clk <= '0';
  wait for clk_period/2;
  clk <= '1';
  wait for clk_period/2;
end process;
-- Stimulus process
stim_proc: process
begin
  -- Reset phase; -- End simulation
  wait;
end process;
end behavioral;
```

21. FILES I/O FOR TESTBENCH

```

-- File I/O for testbenches
use std.textio.all;
process
  file input_file : text open read_mode is "input.txt";
  file output_file : text open write_mode is "output.txt";
  variable line_in : line;
  variable line_out : line;
  variable data : integer;
begin
  while not endfile(input_file) loop
    readline(input_file, line_in);
    read(line_in, data);
    -- Process data
    data := data * 2;
    write(line_out, data);
    writeline(output_file, line_out);
  end loop;
  wait;
end process;
```

22. FINITE STATE MACHINE

```

entity moore is
  port (clk : in bit;
        reset : in bit;
        input_x : in bit;
        output_z : out bit);
end moore;
```



```

architecture behavioral of moore is
  type state_type is (q0,q1,q2);
  signal current_s,next_s: state_type;
begin
```

```

--combinational process to model next-state-logic
process (current_s,input_x)
begin
  case current_s is
    when q0 => --when current state is "q0"
      if(input_x = '0') then next_s <= q0;
      else next_s <= q1;
    end if;
    when q1 => --when current state is "q1"
      if(input_x = '0') then next_s <= q1;
      else next_s <= q2;
    end if;
    when q2 => --when current state is "q2"
      if(input_x = '0') then next_s <= q1;
      else next_s <= q2;
    end if;
  end case;
end process;
--sequential process to describe current-state-logic
process (clk,reset)
begin
  if (reset='1') then
    current_s <= q0; --asynchronous reset
  elsif (clk'event and clk='1') then
    current_s <= next_s; --state change.
  end if;
end process;
```

```

process (current_s) --combinational process to model output-logic
begin
```

```

  case current_s is
    when q0 => output_z <= '0'; --when current state is "q0"
    when q1 => output_z <= '1'; --when current state is "q1"
    when q2 => output_z <= '0'; --when current state is "q2"
  end case;
end process;
end behavioral;
```

23. Best Practices

- Use meaningful names: enable instead of e, data_bus instead of db
- Always use OTHERS in case statements to avoid latches
- Include all inputs in sensitivity lists for combinational logic
- Use STD_LOGIC instead of BIT for flexibility
- Cast STD_LOGIC_VECTOR to UNSIGNED/SIGNED before arithmetic
- Group related signals into records for complex interfaces
- Use generics to make components reusable
- Comment your code to explain the hardware behavior